

Analyzing Performance of Classifiers for Fake News Detection

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Abstract- Fake information is faux or misleading information supplied as news. Fake news is spread on social media and news outlets to boost readership or as a form of psychological warfare. It regularly has the goal of damaging the popularity of person or entity, or earning money via marketing sales. So the sites containing false and misleading information should be detected and filtered out. One way to get around this is to figure out faux news and identify how to better classify them. This paper compares the output of three machine learning techniques that is for k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Naïve Bayes, Logistic Regression on fake news dataset in order to determine which classifier is best for classifying fake news correctly.

Keywords—Machine Learning, k-Nearest Neighbors, Logistic, Naïve Bayes, Weka, Accuracy

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence (AI) that allows computers to learn and improve on their own without having to be explicitly programmed. It is concerned with the creation of computer programmes that can access data and learn on their own. The goal of this research is to identify the best algorithm for classifying the fake news dataset based on various attributes utilising various Machine Learning approaches (ML).

The Internet is a treasure trove of information that is extremely valuable for a variety of reasons. Because of the vast amount of information available on the internet, one must exercise caution when it comes to originality [1]. For a vast number of people all around the world, social media is becoming the primary source of news. Modern social media platforms are very different from traditional news outlets like newspapers in terms of organisation [2]. Fake information is consciously or unintentionally manufactured and disseminated through the internet. Even if it's fraudulent or real, the creation and consumption of information on the internet has increased throughout time [1]. So, there is a need to

classify news since fake news spreads quicker than actual news.

Manually classifying bogus and true news is challenging for a non-expert. The necessity to recognise fake news has grown in importance as a result of its widespread distribution.

The main goal of this research is to present a classifier that uses time and accuracy to detect bogus news. The proposed System is to identify a model that works well for determining if news is fraudulent or authentic.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Smitha. N¹ and Bharath. R¹ proposed feature vectors are generated using a variety of feature engineering approaches such as count vector, TF-IDF, and word embedding. Seven different Machine Learning Classification algorithms are trained to identify news as false or real, and then they are compared based on accuracy, F1 Score, recall, and precision, with the best one being chosen to develop a model to classify news as false or genuine.

Karishnu Poddar², Geraldine Bessie Amali², Umadevi K² suggested a probabilistic and geometric machine learning computational model. In addition, the scores of two distinct vectorizers, count and Term Frequency Inverse Document Format (TF-IDF), will be compared in order to determine the best vectorizer for detecting false news. To increase the scores, English stop words were utilised. To forecast bogus news, various classifiers were utilised, including Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression, and Decision Tree Classifier.

Mykhailo Granik⁵, Volodymyr Mesyura⁵ proved that even a simple artificial intelligence algorithm (such as the naive Bayes classifier) may get good results on a task as crucial as false news categorization. As a result, artificial intelligence approaches may be effective in addressing this critical issue.

Ankit Kesarwani⁶, Sudakar Singh Chauhan⁶, Anil Ramachandran Nair⁶ used the K-Nearest Neighbor classifier, a simple method for detecting bogus news on social media may be found. The identification of features from datasets is an important element of this process since the data mining technique (K-Nearest Neighbor) uses them to categorise news articles on social media.

III. METHODOLOGY

The aim of this study is to classify real and fake news using machine learning techniques [1]. This section explains the approach for categorising fake news based on certain characteristics. As illustrated in Figure 1, the methodology includes multiple phases, including dataset collection, pre-processing, classification, and performance evaluation.

A. WEKA

Weka is a set of data mining-related machine learning techniques. The algorithms can be used to directly apply to a dataset or invoked from Java code. Data pre-processing, classification, regression, clustering, association rules and visualisation are all available in Weka [3]. WEKA allows you to implement a variety of algorithms. One can choose an algorithm, specify the required parameters, and execute it on the dataset.

The statistical result of the model processing would then be provided by WEKA. It comes with a visualisation tool for examining the data [4]. WEKA would provide you with the model's statistics results. It comes with a graphical representation for examining the data. On the same dataset, the multiple models can be used. The outputs of various models can then be compared, and the best model that matches your needs can be chosen [4].

Fig. 1. Methodology for Fake News Classification

B. Dataset Collection

Mainly four attributes are used to classify whether a news is real or fake. The dataset used in this study is taken from the Kaggle repository, and from that 100 instances are taken. This data collection serves as the classifier's training data. The four attributes are date, title, text, label-liar (determines whether the news is real or fake).

C. Pre-Processing

Machine Learning, data pre-processing refers to the process of cleaning and organising raw data in order to make it appropriate for creating and training Machine Learning models. To put it another way, data preparation in Machine Learn is the process of transforming raw data into usable information. The data obtained from the field comprises a number of undesirable elements that lead to incorrect analysis. The data could, for example, contain null fields or columns that are irrelevant to the current study, and so on. As a result, the data must be pre-processed to satisfy the needs of the analysis you're performing. The pre-processing module is where this is done.

D. Classification

The Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis is used to carry out the categorization experiment (WEKA). In this work, we will examine the outcomes of various machine learning algorithms and strategies for false news classification, such as KNN, Logistic Regression and Naive Bayes, to evaluate which method has the highest accuracy for correctly identifying fake and true news.

IV. IMPLIMENTATION

Mainly three classification algorithms are used for comparison they are listed below:

A. *k*-Nearest Neighbors

KNN algorithm is referred to as IBk in Weka (Instance Based Learner). Instead of creating a model, the IBk algorithm produces a forecast for a test instance just-in-time. Since KNN is a lazy learning algorithm it will come under the classifier lazy in weka. The IBk algorithm uses a distance measure to find *k* "close" instances in the training data for each test instance, then makes a prediction based on those instances.

```

Correctly Classified Instances      100      100      %
Incorrectly Classified Instances    0         0      %
Kappa statistic                    1
Mean absolute error                0.0098
Root mean squared error            0.0098
Relative absolute error            2.2462 %
Root relative squared error        2.1016 %
Total Number of Instances         100

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

      TP Rate  FP Rate  Precision  Recall  F-Measure  MCC   ROC Area  PRC Area  Class
      1.000    0.000    1.000     1.000    1.000     1.000  1.000    1.000    fake
      1.000    0.000    1.000     1.000    1.000     1.000  1.000    1.000    real
Weighted Avg.  1.000    0.000    1.000     1.000    1.000     1.000  1.000    1.000

=== Confusion Matrix ===

 a b  <-- classified as
68 0 | a = fake
 0 32 | b = real
    
```

Fig. 2. Classification Accuracy by KNN (IBk)

B. Naïve Bayes:

Naive Bayes classifiers are a class of basic probabilistic classifiers based on the Bayes theorem and strict (naive) independence assumptions between variables in machine learning. Characteristics The Naive Bayes technique is an easy way to construct models. Classifiers are algorithms that allocate problem instances to one of several categories. where the class marks are interpreted as a vector of function values is derived from finite set [5].

```

Correctly Classified Instances      100      100      %
Incorrectly Classified Instances    0         0      %
Kappa statistic                    1
Mean absolute error                0.1542
Root mean squared error            0.1809
Relative absolute error            35.3368 %
Root relative squared error        38.7709 %
Total Number of Instances         100

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

      TP Rate  FP Rate  Precision  Recall  F-Measure  MCC   ROC Area  PRC Area  Class
      1.000    0.000    1.000     1.000    1.000     1.000  1.000    1.000    fake
      1.000    0.000    1.000     1.000    1.000     1.000  1.000    1.000    real
Weighted Avg.  1.000    0.000    1.000     1.000    1.000     1.000  1.000    1.000

=== Confusion Matrix ===

 a b  <-- classified as
68 0 | a = fake
 0 32 | b = real
    
```

Fig. 3. Classification Accuracy by Naïve Bayes

C. Logistic Regression:

Logistic regression has a number of advantages, including probability modelling, the ability to include features that are dependent and the ease of updating the model with new data. Although logistic regression is defined as a binary logistic regression with binary target variables, it may also predict two more types of target variables. For higher accuracy, logistic regression requires a huge data set, while Naive Bayes can work for small datasets as well. So the accuracy of logistic regression will be lower compared to other algorithms hat is used.

```

Correctly Classified Instances      72       72      %
Incorrectly Classified Instances    28       28      %
Kappa statistic                    0.2857
Mean absolute error                0.3244
Root mean squared error            0.4032
Relative absolute error            74.3164 %
Root relative squared error        86.4294 %
Total Number of Instances         100

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

      TP Rate  FP Rate  Precision  Recall  F-Measure  MCC   ROC Area  PRC Area  Class
      0.882    0.625    0.750     0.882    0.811    0.300  0.795    0.901    fake
      0.375    0.118    0.600     0.375    0.462    0.300  0.795    0.644    real
Weighted Avg.  0.720    0.463    0.702     0.720    0.699    0.300  0.795    0.819

=== Confusion Matrix ===

 a b  <-- classified as
60 8 | a = fake
20 12 | b = real
    
```

Fig. 4. Classification Accuracy by Logistic Regression.

V. RESULT

The classification of this dataset was done to classify fake and real news based on some attributes. The dataset had a total of 4 nominal attributes. Result of the testing using evaluation on the training dataset indicate that KNN has same accuracy level to Naïve Bayes by 100%, and Logistic Regression has 72% accuracy.

However, for higher accuracy, logistic regression requires a huge data set and we have taken 100 instances

only. Since, the KNN method is faster than Naïve in terms of processing speed. Below Table1 shows the performance comparison chart of algorithms on fake news dataset.

TABLE I. RECEIVED RESULT

ML Techniques	Accuracy	Time Taken to Build a Model
KNN (IBk)	100 %	0s
Naïve Bayes	100 %	0.03s
Logistic Regression	72 %	0.06s

- [5] Mykhailo Granik, Volodymyr Mesyura “Fake News Detection Using Naive Bayes Classifier”
- [6] Ankit Kesarwani, Sudakar Singh Chauhan, Anil Ramachandran Nair “Fake News Detection on Social Media using K-Nearest Neighbor Classifier”

VI. CONCLUSION

In this proposed system three different Machine learning classifier algorithms are used in order to compare the accuracy. The fake news dataset was taken from the Kaggle library, and various machine learning approaches were used to differentiate fake and actual news. The methods and findings of a fake news classification experiment based on title, text, and date were discussed in this paper. This comparison study gives a greater understanding of how different machine learning models function and how they perform in real-world scenarios thanks to this comparison analysis.

VII. FUTURE WORK

Only a few instances are taken into account in this proposed scheme, and attributes such as title, date, and text are compared at the same time. In the future, more instances and attributes, such as the site's url, will be included in the comparison.

VIII. REFERENCES

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